

Innovative post-deposition treatment for local doping control in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ by a combined temperature-voltage method

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Abstract:

The lattice mismatch between CdS and kesterite materials results in a faulty growth of CdS on top of kesterite and detrimental interface defects. The most common strategy for interface passivation and to achieve a recrystallization of the window layer is the use of soft thermal treatments (typically at $T < 300^\circ\text{C}$). Thermal treatments in a wide range of temperatures and different atmospheres have been performed on the bare absorber, CdS/CZTSe heterojunction and full device, alleviating this problem and improving the photovoltaic performance. Nevertheless, kesterite materials present two polymorphs leading to a low temperature order-disorder phase transition with an impact on the optoelectronic properties.

In this work, we firstly explore the role of this phase transition and study the effects of a full device heat treatment required for interface passivation. A post-deposition thermal treatment is performed at temperatures above the phase transition critical temperature (200°C), then the degree of disorder is controlled by either quenching (270°C) or slowly cooling down the samples (170°C). This first study allows de-coupling the role of O/D in the kesterite materials when modified after material synthesis from the role of interface passivation and window layer re-crystallization. Hence, we identify the heat treatment as the ideal platform to modify the shallow doping defect concentrations (Cu_{Zn} , V_{Cu} and Zn_{Cu}) without strongly affecting the recombination center concentration (Sn_{Zn}). This additionally points towards the importance of the thermal history of kesterite materials for photovoltaic applications.

In a second part, we propose an innovative method to control the shallow doping locally by simultaneously applying temperature and voltage, inducing the drift of ionized Cu-Zn defects. The experimental results are rigorously discussed and reproduced using a numerical model with SCAPS-1D by including bulk recombination effects. Finally, the impact of the shallow doping gradient on the band structure and recombination rates is presented, revealing an increased band bending at the CZTSe/CdS and stablishing it is a promising strategy to enhance charge carrier separation in kesterite solar cells as an alternative to band grading strategies. This method presents for first time an innovative method to control the shallow defect profiling to improve the photovoltaic efficiency of a CZTSe device, opening perspectives for any other photovoltaic technology.

1. Introduction:

$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ (CZTSe) is a non-toxic material, constituted by earth abundant elements and presenting high absorption coefficients ($>10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), resulting in an exceptional candidate for mass production of Thin-Film Solar Cells (TFSC) for Building and Product Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV and PIPV), as well as a bottom cell in tandem solar cells [1]. Currently, the kesterite/CZTSe family is the emerging TFSC technology presenting the higher power conversion efficiencies (PCE) and the properties of the material have been thoroughly studied throughout the last decade. [2]–[4]

However, CZTSe solar cells are hindered by a high open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) deficit, related to low minority carrier lifetimes consequence of high non-radiative recombination rates. Various strategies aiming to mitigate the impact of non-radiative recombination in different regions of the device (CdS/CZTSe interface, CZTSe bulk and back contact) have been explored through the past decade, leading to promising results in the reduction of recombination rates in CZTSe solar cells. The most relevant advances improving kesterite efficiencies have been achieved by a precise control of the synthesis route of kesterite, normally enhancing grain growth, controlling the secondary phase segregation and the recombination center concentration by either precisely controlling Sn oxidation state or via extrinsic (co)-doping or alloying (H, Li, Ge, Ag). [5]–[14] These recent advances in the kesterite research community reveal that non-radiative recombination rates can be effectively reduced by a precise control of the reaction pathway. The formation of kesterite is a key step in the processing since it is well-known that Sn-related defects and specifically Sn_{Zn} recombination centers dominate the lifetime in kesterite compounds.[15] While non-radiative recombination might be the limiting factor for CZTSe, the impact of modifying kesterite synthesis route on other relevant parameters (such as doping, mobility, grain boundary passivation and interface recombination) cannot be disregarded and the development of methods to control these parameters could be a key processing step for enhancing the PCE of kesterite devices. In fact, the scientists of South Wales University have found that non-radiative recombination due to Sn_{Zn} is not limiting the performance of CZTSe, instead, they identify low hole concentration and un-passivated grain boundaries as the main limiting factors. [16]. Nonetheless, in equilibrium conditions, the concentration of Sn_{Zn} defect is reduced for CZTSe with a low hole concentration as discussed elsewhere [12], [15], [17]. Therefore, increasing the hole concentration of the as-grown CZTSe may not lead to further improvements in PCE due to increased recombination rates. Furthermore, the high native concentration of Sn_{Zn} under all conditions could still limit the recombination rates once GBs are passivated. Although out of the scope of this work, the implementation of a reactive post-deposition treatment (PDT), e.g. alkali-halides, which could lead to the passivation of defective GBs. [18]–[21]

In this work, we investigate and characterize the effects of a soft ($T < 300^\circ\text{C}$) post deposition treatment (PDT) step since it is possibly a key strategy to reduce the V_{oc} deficit of kesterite solar cells. The effects of the PDT on window layer re-crystallization, interface element intermixing, Cu-Zn order disorder (O/D), and alkali out-diffusion will be thoroughly discussed in a first part of the manuscript.

1.1. The PDT: An strategy designed for interface passivation

A thorough characterization of the PDT on the CZTSe of our group was provided by Neuschitzer et al. [22], which focused on the effects of a thermal annealing at 200° , i.e. the O/D critical temperature (T_c). An efficiency improvement from 2% to 8% was observed after the PDT. Many remarkable effects were reported: i) the observation of a Zn-poor surface after CdS chemical bath deposition (CBD) and a Zn-enrichment and Cu-depletion after the PDT. ii) The surface of the CZTSe is Cd soaked after the PDT. Surface Cd-soaking is a strategy that has additionally been investigated by other groups yielding promising results. [23] iii) A Cu-enrichment of the CdS is

observed. While CdS can become photoactive upon Cu doping, most of the literature reveals that as deposited CdS performs better than Cu-doped CdS [23], possibly due to the presence of Cu_{Cd} defects acting as compensating acceptor and tuning CdS behavior towards intrinsic/insulating and therefore increasing series resistance (R_s). However, by properly designing the PDT, the adequate element intermixing at the interface can lead to beneficial passivation effects. In fact, a CZTSe-Cd_{Poor}/CZTSe-Cd_{Soak}/CuS/CdS buried junction was naturally obtained by South Wales University group during AZO deposition (150°C for 90 min) with a subsequent remarkable improvement on the efficiency of the device.[24] iv) A Cu depletion of grain boundaries is observed, probably impacted beneficially by Na out diffusion from the SLG resulting in Na accumulation at both the grain boundaries and the interfaces (alkali cations are well-known for the passivation effects in CZTSe grain boundaries) [18], [21]. (v) CdS and ITO re-crystallization. (vi) CZTSe O/D transition was observed via Raman spectroscopy. Currently, it is well-known that different Cu-Zn O/D can lead to different hole concentration and potentially affect charge carrier mobility [17].

1.2. CZTSe: A material with an O/D phase transition

CZTSe is a material which presents a low temperature phase transition and the impact of the changes in the optoelectronic properties for differently ordered CZTSe are extremely relevant for the photovoltaic PCE. The kesterite structure with symmetry group I4 presents alternating Cu-Zn and Cu-Sn planes bonded to tetragonally coordinated Se atoms. Due to the similar Cu⁺ and Zn²⁺ atomic radius (135 pm) and electronic configuration ([Ar]3d¹⁰4s⁰) the Wyckoff positions of Cu and Zn in the Cu-Zn planes (Cu (2c) and Zn (2d)) are easily occupied by the other cation. This is the main reason why a degree of disorder is present in all experimentally synthesized CZTSe (the most ordered CZTSe is around 80%)[17]. The phase transition presents no discontinuities in the order parameter Q (1), thus the O/D phase transition is considered of second order. Note that the out of plane O/D can be regarded as a partial transition to the stannite phase, generally in competition with kesterite due to the low energy difference between both phases. Nevertheless, stannite inclusions are not regarded as detrimental for PCE due to stannite band gap (E_g) being higher than the one for kesterite phase.

$$Q = \frac{[Cu_{2c} + Zn_{2d}] - [Zn_{2c} + Cu_{2d}]}{[Cu_{2c} + Zn_{2d}] + [Zn_{2c} + Cu_{2d}]} \quad (1)$$

The O/D phase transition, with a T_c of approximately 200°C for CZTSe, leads to a mixed occupation (50%) of Cu and Zn in the Cu (2c) and Zn (2d), which becomes a 4d site. Therefore, a fully disordered kesterite with Q=0, which belongs to a different symmetry group (I4_{2m}), is a different phase. In a partially disordered phase, Cu and Zn atoms exchange in-plane positions, resulting in proliferation of Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu} defects in equivalent concentrations, generally in the form of [Cu_{Zn}⁺+Zn_{Cu}⁻] defect cluster. This defect cluster presence does not necessarily lead to detrimental effects in the solar cell behavior, however, the phase transition leads to other changes with a relevant impact on the optoelectronic properties of CZTSe, as will be discussed in the following sections. It is worth noting that during this phase transition, only Cu and Zn cation mobility is thermally activated. Sn atoms present a bigger atomic radius (145 pm) and a higher atomic mass (118 a.u.), and thus remain fixed and therefore the concentration of detrimental Sn-related defects remains unchanged. Higher temperatures (>600°C) are needed to thermally activate Sn disorder in the kesterite family. [17]

The effects of the PDT in two identical samples, one quenched at the PDT temperature and the other slowly cooled down will be used to de-couple the effects of CZTSe order-disorder (O/D) from buffer and window layer re-crystallization effects as well as interface passivation.

1.3. The purpose of graded solar cells

The concept of graded solar cells was popularized for the Cu(In,Ga)(S,Se)_2 photovoltaic technology, and similar strategies have been pursued in CZTSe. [25] The CIGSSe and CZTSe structure generally use CdS/i-ZnO as an electron transport layer (ETL) and MoSe_2 as the hole transport layer (HTL). In the case of CIGSSe, a control of both Ga/In and S/Se content profile lead to significant PCE improvements. Both the Ga and S profiles are used to locally manipulate the band-gap to generate a specific band gradient that maximizes charge carrier separation and minimizes recombination.[25] The gradient is the following: The CIGSSe is S-rich near the CIGSSe/CdS interface, to shift the VBM downwards in energy and reduce the concentration of holes near the ETL interface, which reduces space-charge region (SCR) and interface (IF) recombination while keeping the CBM practically unaffected.[26], [27] On the other hand, Ga incorporation shifts the CBM upwards in energy. Therefore, Ga content starts at the minimum and it is linearly increased towards the HTL. This acts as an electron barrier and reduces the electron concentration near the HTL improving the charge carrier collection as well as reducing back contact recombination.

Hence, the band gap grading strategies attracted the interest of the kesterite community and S/Se and Ge/Sn grading strategies, which have the same effects on the CZTSe band structure than the S/Se and Ga/In ratios in CIGS were developed. Nevertheless, the tendency of S to completely alloy with CZTSe and the scarcity of Ge suppose a problem to efficiently develop a band gap graded CZTSe. [28]–[30]

1.4. Cu-Zn defect graded solar cells

In this work, an innovative grading strategy will be proposed and studied. As will be demonstrated, the kesterite majority carrier concentration is strongly affected by the Cu/Zn disorder, where disordered kesterite presents more shallow acceptor states. [17], [31] This is a consequence of an increased concentration of V_{Cu} and Cu_{Zn} defects. Zn_{Cu} defects are also increased in concentration, but in the commonly used Cu-poor, Zn-rich, Sn-stoichiometric conditions, the Fermi Energy is pinned closer to the VBM for disordered kesterite. [17] Commonly, the O/D transition also affects the E_{G} , since the Cu-3d states determine the position of the VBM. However, the E_{G} only changes for a few meV, therefore it does not lead to any of the major effects caused by O/D. [17], [31].

In this work, the O/D transition will be used to improve the charge carrier selectivity of the device, aiming to implement an innovative and simple grading strategy in the shallow doping concentration if the Cu_{Zn} , V_{Cu} (shallow acceptors) and Zn_{Cu} (shallow donor) defects could be graded throughout the absorber. This concept will be further discussed throughout the manuscript. As will be shown, simultaneously applying heat (above O/D T_c) to activate the mobility of ionized Cu and Zn defects and voltage can selectively drift ionized defects towards the one of transport layer interface depending on the charge state (positive or negative). Hence, a gradient in the defect concentration should, in theory, be observed. The effects of a combined heat+ voltage PDT on the illuminated J-V curves and external quantum efficiency (EQE) are presented throughout the work. The effects of a shallow doping grading on the photovoltaic performance of a CZTSe solar cell will be discussed using quasi-quantitative analysis with SCAPS-1D software to probe the effect in three different cases: i) Radiative Limit, ii) bulk non-radiative recombination and iii) interface recombination. Experimental and numerically calculated J-V curves and EQE will be compared, a detailed discussion of the effects on the band structure and recombination rates of the device will be provided.

2. Methods

Sample Preparation

CZTSe films were grown on Mo-coated (DC magnetron sputtering, Alliance AC450) soda-lime glass substrates (SLG). Standard Cu/Sn/Cu/Zn metallic precursor stack was sequentially deposited on top of a Mo tri-layer by DC sputtering. Back contact optimization and structure is developed in Ref. [32] The precursor composition and thickness was calibrated and measured by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF, Fischerscope XDV), precursors with Cu/(Sn+Zn)~0.72 and Zn/Sn~1.05 ratios were used. The as-deposited stack was subjected to reactive annealing under Se+Sn atmosphere: 100 mg of Se (Alfa-Aesar powder, 200 mesh, 99.999%) and 5 mg of Sn (Alfa-Aesar powder, 100 mesh, 99.995%). A two-step thermal profile using graphite boxes (69 cm³ in volume) in a conventional three zone tubular furnace was used for the synthesis of CZTSe: first step with dwelling time of 30 min with a ramp of 20 °C/min and temperature of 400 °C at 1.5 mbar (Ar flux), and second step with dwelling time 15 min with a ramp of 20 °C/min and temperature of 550 °C under Ar static pressure (1 bar). Solar cell devices finished by depositing 50 nm CdS by chemical bath deposition (CBD) preceded by (NH₄)₂S etching, followed by deposition of 50 nm i-ZnO and 200 nm ITO by DC-pulsed sputtering (Alliance CT100).[33], [34] To perform the optoelectronic characterization, 3 x 3 mm² sub-cells were mechanically scribed using a manual microdiamond scribe (OEG Optical Metrology MR200). Neither antireflective coating nor metallic grids were used for the optoelectronic characterization of the devices. Different hotplate annealing in air conditions were performed on the full devices for 25 min, including the heating ramp from room temperature. To separate the effects on the O/D of CZTSe from the interface passivation and window layer re-crystallization different PDT profiles were performed: two samples quenched at 250 °C and 270 °C (quench) and other two slowly cooled down from the same temperatures to 170 °C (SCD), well below the O/D T_c. The quenching procedure consisted in removing the samples from the hotplate to rapidly cool down. For the slow cooling down the hotplate temperature was reduced at a rate of 1 °C/min. To apply voltage a power source was connected to the front (ITO) and back contact (Mo/In) and a constant voltage was applied during the PDT.

Device and Material Characterization

Dark and illuminated current-voltage (J–V) curves were measured using a calibrated Sun 3000 class AAA solar simulator (Abet Technologies, 25 °C, AM1.5G illumination) under ambient conditions. The spectral response was measured using a Bentham PVE300 system calibrated with Si and Ge photodiodes in order to obtain the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the solar cells. Reflectance was measured using a built in integrating sphere accessory in the spectral response equipment.

Device modelling

Illuminated J-V curves and EQE spectra were calculated by using drift-diffusion program (SCAPS-1D). The device structure, material parameters, and the recombination center properties are obtained from a single fabrication process[8] and its reliability is tested and published elsewhere. To explore the effects of a linear doping grading at the absorber layer (from back contact to front contact) a linear shallow doping gradient is implemented in the CZTSe layer (from 10¹⁵ to 10¹⁷ cm⁻³ for the p to p⁺ profile and vice versa for the p⁺ to p). Interface and bulk recombination is also considered in this work; details are also published elsewhere. The concentration of both defects is determined by fitting the V_{oc} of the reference cells. In this work, the interface defect concentration is approximated to be 4·10¹¹ cm⁻² and the bulk defect concentration is approximated to 8·10¹⁵ cm⁻³.

3. Results

3.1. Effects of thermal treatment

In this section, to decouple the effects of the PDT on the window layer, CZTSe/CdS interface and CZTSe bulk different PDT profile have been performed on solar cell devices. The effects of the PDT and the differences between quench and SCD are discussed in the SI.

Nevertheless, the most relevant observations are described in the following points:

1. The application of a PDT is associated to a drastic reduction of the series resistance (R_s), resulting in FF with double the values independently on the chosen PDT configuration. This could be associated to ITO re-crystallization reducing lateral resistance losses.[35], [36] Another effect reducing the series resistance could be a reduced contact resistance associated to a lower electron barrier product of element inter-diffusion at the CZTSe/CdS interface[22]–[24], [37]. Both effects might contribute to the R_s reduction and the FF improvement.
2. The changes in the ideality factor, from above 3 to approximately 1.5 indicate that the main recombination pathway before the PDT is interface/multistep dominated. After the PDT, devices are dominated by SCR/Bulk recombination. This further supports the observations that the PDT is basically required to improve the window layer and interfacial properties and not necessarily required to improve CZTSe bulk. The observed improvement of the V_{oc} after the PDT could be closely related to interface passivation.
3. The O/D transition of CZTSe can be used to control the hole density and is responsible for the observed V_{oc} and J_{sc} interplay. [17], [31], [38]. A reduced collection length can be inferred from the EQE spectra for the quenched and more disordered CZTSe, related to a reduced space charge region (SCR) width. C-V profiling confirms that disordered CZTSe presents a higher majority carrier concentration. The impact of O/D in the electron mobility remains unclear, the increase in $[Cu_{Zn}+Zn_{Cu}]$ defect cluster could detrimentally impact mobility.[39]
4. The bulk recombination center concentration (Sn_{Zn}) seems not to be strongly affected by the O/D and the thermal treatment, this is to be expected since Sn atoms remain immobile in the range of temperature considered here. [17]
5. The grain boundaries could be electrically passivated during the PDT due to Na out-diffusion and accumulation at the defect sites. However, grain boundaries are not the limiting factor before the PDT and the passivation effects cannot be probed.

To summarize, a thorough description and characterization of the effects of a PDT to the CZTSe/CdS based device as well as the effects of O/D of CZTSe in the optoelectronic parameters is provided. It has been demonstrated that a PDT is required to improve the CZTSe/CdS interface and the window layer properties and it is independent from the cooling down rate of the sample. However, the thermal history of CZTSe absorbers influences the degree of O/D with a direct impact in the doping and therefore in the V_{oc} and J_{sc} .

3.2. Investigation of the new concept: Doping graded solar cells

In this section, the effects of the thermal PDT will be combined with an applied voltage. As discussed previously, only Cu and Zn mobility are activated above the O/D T_c of CZTSe and the shallow Cu-Zn defect concentration depend on the temperature of the PDT. The presence of an electric field (applied voltage) during the PDT is expected to induce a drift of mobile and ionized defects like Cu_{Zn}^- , V_{Cu}^- (Acceptors, negatively charged) and Zn_{Cu}^+ (donor, positively charged), which can be considered as charged particles. It is straightforward that these ionized defects should re-distribute, since an electric field is acting as a driving force leading to the accumulation of charged particles that screen the external electric field, until a steady-state is achieved. Alternatively, one could consider that the applied voltage modifies the hole and electron quasi-fermi levels (QFL) throughout the CZTSe absorber. Therefore, when a positive (negative) bias is applied to the front contact (by approximating the gradient in electrochemical potential as linear throughout the CZTSe absorber) an electron injection (depletion) occurs near the CZTSe/CdS interface. A gradient in electrochemical potential is similar to a gradient in the (out of equilibrium) Fermi energy. The changes in electrochemical potential tune the formation energy of Cu and Zn related defects and therefore donor (acceptor) defects should increase the formation energy near the CZTSe/CdS interface and oppositely for the back contact interface region. Therefore, the presence of an electric field during the PDT could easily lead to a gradient in the shallow defect concentration of CZTSe.

Figure 1. Optoelectronic parameters after the PDT for different applied voltages in a sub-cell. To experimentally realize the doping graded structure a combined voltage + heat treatment is applied to a specific sub-cell, while the conventional thermal treatment is applied to all the sub-cells in

the sample, which are used as a reference. An image of the experimental set-up for the combined voltage + heat treatment is presented in SI.

In this part of the manuscript, the effects of the nominal graded shallow doping concentration from p^+ to p (p to p^+) generated by a PDT with positive (negative) voltage will be studied. The changes in the optoelectronic parameters induced by the presence of voltage during the PDT are presented in **Figure 1**. An increase in the V_{oc} can be observed for sub-cells where a negative bias was applied, i.e. with increased presence of acceptor defects near the CdS/CZTSe interface, (p to p^+ doping). The V_{oc} and FF appear to follow a similar trend. This is an indication that the variation in FF with the applied bias does not relate to series/shunt resistance changes, but is instead directly related to changes in the recombination rates. This will be further investigated in the following sections. Oppositely, the J_{sc} is slightly decreased by the p to p^+ doping grading in the CZTSe absorber. The changes in J_{sc} are limited, yet trends are nevertheless observed and will be further discussed in the following sections. The effects for sub-cells where positive voltage was applied (p^+ to p doping) are the opposite. Note that the effects for $-0.3V$ are almost negligible and at least $-0.6V$ are necessary to observe significant changes in the optoelectronic properties. This is in contrast with the behavior for the sub-cells with a positive voltage, where $+0.3V$ is enough to observe significant changes. This points to the fact that the rectifying behavior of the CZTSe device could limit the effect of applied negative voltage on the optoelectronic properties of the devices.

The experimental J-V curves and EQE spectra for three representative sub-cells are presented in **Figure 2**. The J-V curves confirm the fact that the V_{oc} is increased for a negative voltage (p to p^+) and reduced for positive the voltage (p^+ to p). Slight changes in the J_{sc} can be observed, the differences in the reverse bias conditions are more remarkable. The EQE spectra does not reveal significant differences between the reference and the negative bias samples, suggesting that the rectifying behavior of the devices could limit the experimentally achieved grading to values that basically affect the V_{oc} and have a minor effect on the current collection. Nevertheless, the changes observed for the positive bias ($+0.3V$) reveal an improved carrier collection, as would be expected for a p^+ to p doping grading. However, the observed decrease in V_{oc} is not expected by the formation of a doping grading and further investigation is needed to identify its origin.

Figure 2. a) Representative experimental J-V curves for different applied voltages during PDT. b) External quantum efficiency of the same representative sub-cells.

The band gap of the absorber layers was extracted from the EQE spectra by two different methods and are presented in **Figure SI**. i) Inflection point of the long wavelength region of the EQE spectra and ii) Tauc plot. A clear difference in E_G can be observed for the cell treated with positive

bias, whereas the negative bias cells present the no significant differences from the reference cells E_G given the resolution of the EQE equipment (5 nm or 0.005 eV). The different E_G for the positive bias cell could be related to a Cu accumulation at the back contact shifting the VBM downwards in energy and therefore increasing E_G . If bias induced defect migration is considered, the accumulation of Cu at the back contact is a consequence of Cu_{Zn} defect accumulation, which generally is the dominant acceptor defect in CZTSe. An accumulation of VCu should be also present, however, Cu_{Zn} defect dominates the effects on the E_G due to a higher native concentration. In the case of negative bias cells, the rectifying behavior of the CZTSe/CdS junction might confine the effects of bias to the SCR, this will be further discussed in the following sections.

3.3. Modelling J-V curves and EQE spectra

To confirm if a shallow defect grading is the cause of this experimental behavior, SCAPS-1D J-V curves are calculated using a quasi-quantitative device baseline developed in our group and based on the champion device from [8], with implemented bulk and interface non-radiative recombination using parameters from the literature and defect concentration being the only floating parameter.

Figure 3. Experimental and SCAPS-1D calculated J-V curves. The effects of a realistic but arbitrary shallow doping grading are studied. A linear doping grading (from back contact to front contact) is implemented in the CZTSe layer (from 10^{15} to 10^{17} cm^{-3} for the p to p+ profile and viceversa for the p+ to p). Different recombination effects, at the interface or at the bulk, are explored. The experimental J-V curves and EQE spectra with different applied voltages are matched by the numerical curves when bulk recombination is implemented. The p to p+ profiling seems to be overestimated in the numerical analysis as compared to the experiment, this is discussed throughout the text.

The SCAPS-1D calculated J-V curves with different shallow doping profiles are presented in **Figure 3**. For the device modelling of a CZTSe solar cell in the radiative limit, no major changes in the V_{oc} can be observed. Nonetheless, a slight improvement (50 mV) in the V_{oc} can be achieved implementing doping grading. However, the short circuit current is strongly affected due to the doping gradient, revealing that it can strongly affect carrier selectivity. Naturally, in the ideal case, the p^+ to p grading can be used to improve photovoltaic performance, as expected by the carrier selectivity rules.[40] When interface recombination is introduced, the V_{oc} remains practically unaffected by the doping grading (yet the interfacial defect has a relevant impact on the V_{oc} in the concentrations used in this work, limiting it to 0.42 V for all cases). Note that the interfacial defect is reported as acceptor in the literature and thus might be increasing in concentration with negative applied voltage. [41] Although not investigated in this manuscript, a proliferation of this defect in the CZTSe/CdS might lead to fermi level pinning at the interface regardless of the doping profile, leading to a V_{oc} of 0.42V, as observed in the experimental results. On the other hand, even if an interfacial defect is included, the effects on the carrier selectivity are similar to the ideal case, as can be seen in the J_{sc} differences. In contrast with the two previous cases, implementing bulk non-radiative recombination is strictly necessary to reproduce the behavior of the experimental J-V curves. Both the increase of J_{sc} and the decrease of V_{oc} for the p^+ to p grading (and vice versa for the p to p^+) can be observed. It is easy to notice that the reduction in current for the p to p^+ calculations are more marked than the experimental one, suggesting again that the p to p^+ gradient might be limited by the rectifying behavior of the solar cells in the experimental case, limiting the effects of the applied bias to the depletion region.

To further investigate the effects of a doping grading on the behavior of a CZTSe solar cell, EQE spectra are also calculated with SCAPS-1D in the same doping configurations than in the J-V curve analysis. Similarly, the p to p^+ grading might be overestimated as compared to the experimental results. It is worth noticing that the p to p^+ grading can lead to improvements in J_{sc} associated to the enhanced collection of long wavelength photons even if it presents low diffusion lengths related to low carrier lifetimes, as in the case where non-radiative bulk recombination is implemented. In fact, the EQE trends can only be reproduced if bulk non-radiative recombination is implemented. Indicating again that bulk recombination centers dominate the transport properties of CZTSe solar cells. Consequently, only the ideal and bulk recombination models will be compared in the following sections.

3.4. Band structure and recombination rates

Figure 4. Equilibrium band structures of a CZTSe/CdS heterojunction with the different shallow doping profiles. Note that the solid, dashed and dotted lines correspond to flat, p to p⁺ and p⁺ to p profiles. a) Ideal case and b) bulk recombination included. A remarkable increase of the band bending at the CZTSe/CdS interface can be observed. The p⁺ to p doping profile allows to increase the SCR width without compromising the V_{oc} in the ideal case. The drastically reduced carrier collection of the p to p⁺ profile could be related to the band bending near the rear interface.

To unveil the effects of the doping grading on the carrier collection, band structures in equilibrium and under no illumination for the ideal and the non-radiative bulk recombination cases are shown in **Figure 4**. From the ideal case it can be easily observed that an increased band bending at the interface can be achieved by the p⁺ to p grading profile. The SCR width is reduced for the p to p⁺ leading to a reduced current. Note that this method allows to tune the band bending at the CZTSe/CdS interface with a marginal effect in the V_{oc}, at least if bulk recombination is low. When bulk recombination is implemented in the model, the band bending in the case of the p⁺ to p is increased, being the more noticeable effect and one possible cause for the decreased V_{oc} in the experiment. In the case of p to p⁺ profile a hole barrier/electron trap appears near the back contact, with an additional effect on the reduction of the modelled J_{sc}, in addition to the reduced band bending at the front interface. To shed light on why a V_{oc} loss is observed in the experimental case the Generation-Recombination rates in the Maximum Power Point conditions are presented in **Figure 5**. As compared to the constant doping profile, recombination rates at the SCR are higher. In the case of the p⁺ to p there is a region of approximately 250 nm (Space Charge Region) where the Shockley-Read-Hall recombination rates are approximately 2.5 greater than in the constant case. This is probably the cause for the lowered V_{oc} in this case. Therefore, in order for a Cu-Zn defect grading profile to improve the PCE of a CZTSe based device a reduced recombination center, to at least less than 10¹⁵ cm⁻³, corresponding to a lifetime of 1.1 ns and a diffusion length of 330 nm, needs to be achieved. Presenting strategies to reduce the recombination center concentration in CZTSe is out of the scope of this work. Nevertheless, as discussed previously, the minority carrier lifetime of CZTSe should not be strongly affected by a soft PDT. Naturally, if the bulk lifetime is increased, the effects of a gradient in the shallow doping concentration might become more relevant and assist to improve the PCE of CZTSe solar cells.

Figure 5. Left) Generation (green) and recombination (SRH) rates for the different doping profiles. **Right)** SRH recombination ratio of the graded doping profiles to the linear doping. Note that recombination near the CZTSe/CdS is increased near the interface due to an increase in the SCR width, where SRH recombination rates are enhanced due to $n\tau_p \approx p\tau_n$. [42]

4. Discussion

The implementation of CZTSe synthesis strategies to reduce Sn_{Zn} concentration in CZTSe record cells have resulted in a low doping profile and un-passivated grain boundaries. These recent findings point towards the fact that kesterite materials might need of post synthesis processing steps to tune the hole concentration, passivate the grain boundaries and reduce interface recombination. In this work we focus on a full device PDT and observe that the PCE improvement is directly related to i) a reduction of R_s associated to interface element intermixing or CdS and ITO recrystallization and ii) an interplay between J_{sc} and V_{oc} consequence of different order parameter Q , which directly affects the hole concentration.

In more mature TFSC a constant hole concentration profile is also a limiting factor. However, CBM and VBM grading strategies have led to further improvements in the PCE. Unfortunately, for CZTSe these strategies are more complicated and expensive. As a substitute for compositional grading in solar cells, we propose for a first time and investigate a gradient profile in the hole concentration. The absorber material CZTSe O/D phase transition at temperatures below the PDT is an ideal platform for this conceptualization. The implementation of electric bias during the PDT leads to a potential drift of ionized Cu-Zn defects in the CZTSe matrix, which have been demonstrated to control the hole concentration in CZTSe.

While unequivocally demonstrating the presence of a gradient in the defect concentration is experimentally hard, investigating the effects of a doping gradient profile is relatively easy by using numerical simulations. The experimental behavior has been reproduced by implementing an arbitrary but realistic doping profile along with non-radiative bulk recombination, which is known to dominate the transport properties of CZTSe. Therefore, this work showcases the robustness of the SCAPS-1D model of our group to investigate the effects of changes in parameters that are usually not experimentally accessible, as in the case of this work.

4.1. How to optimize doping graded CZTSe in the radiative limit

Sample	V_{oc}	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Ref	0.59	37.74	78.28	17.29
p to p ⁺	0.60	34.77	78.37	16.25
p ⁺ to p	0.60	39.18	79.44	18.68
p ⁺ to p (Optimized)	0.65	38.76	80.78	20.33

Figure 6. Behavior of an ideal CZTSe solar cell with and without a linear doping grading in two different directions. Black) Non-Graded $N_A=3 \cdot 10^{16}$. Red) Graded: N_A at BC= $1 \cdot 10^{15}$ N_A at FC= $1 \cdot 10^{17}$. Orange) N_A at BC= $1 \cdot 10^{17}$ N_A at FC= $1 \cdot 10^{17}$. Green) Optimized Grading \rightarrow N_A at BC= $1 \cdot 10^{18}$ N_A at FC= $1 \cdot 10^{14}$.

Finally, the effects of a doping gradient from the back contact to front contact for an ideal CZTSe (radiative limit) are presented in **Figure 6**, the values chosen 10^{15} and 10^{17} cm^{-3} throughout the

work are doping concentrations that could be experimentally achieved. As can be observed, an increased hole concentration at the back contact and a lowered concentration in the front contact can increase the uniform doping concentration by more than 1% absolute PCE, mainly due to improvements in J_{sc} , suggesting enhanced carrier selectivity. As observed previously, a p to p⁺ doping, results in a lower J_{sc} and a poorer carrier selectivity. For this device structures, almost no improvements in V_{oc} are observed. After combinatorial optimization and as shown in **Figure 6** it is found that a grading of $1 \cdot 10^{18}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm⁻³ is enough to saturate the system in terms of PCE. Resulting in a maximum of 20.33% PCE. An absolute 2% improvement in PCE could be realized without modifying the ETL. Thus, it is shown that a doping grading of CZTSe absorber could lead to an enhanced PCE and that this grading could be adjusted in order to suit its transport layers.

5. Conclusion

In this work, a thorough revision of the effects of a thermal post deposition treatment in a CZTSe/CdS device is presented. The effects of well-known interface passivation, window layer re-crystallization and Cu-Zn order/disorder are observed in the performed optoelectronic characterization. It is noted that a PDT could be used as an effective method to tune the carrier concentration of CZTSe without detrimentally affecting other parameters. To further study the effects of PDT on the doping, in a second part, a method for the local control of shallow donor and acceptor defects consisting in the thermal activation Cu-Zn mobility and further application of electric field to selectively drift ionized Cu and Zn ionized defects towards the desired interface is proposed. The optoelectronic characterization reveals beneficial effects in the carrier collection (J_{sc}) and a decrease in the V_{oc} for positive bias and vice versa for negative bias. Quasi-quantitative drift-diffusion numerical analysis reveals that is possible to reproduce the experimental results by implementing a linear gradient of net shallow acceptor concentration (from 10^{17} cm⁻³ at the back contact and 10^{15} cm⁻³ at the front contact or vice versa) and bulk non-radiative recombination to the calculation parameters. We find that as long as the recombination center concentration is low, the shallow doping gradient from p⁺ at the back contact to p at the front contact is revealed as a promising strategy to boost carrier collection efficiency without compromising the V_{oc} . This method presents for first time an innovative method to control the shallow defect profiling to improve the photovoltaic efficiency of a CZTSe device, opening perspectives for any other photovoltaic technology.

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